

Redox Indicators in Titrations with Dichloramine-T

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Naphthidine, dimethylnaphthidine, dimethylnaphthidinedisulphonic acid, *o*-dianisidine, quinoline yellow, diphenylbenzidine and amaranth have been proposed as indicators in titrations of arsenic(III), iron(II), antimony(III), hydroquinone, hydrazinium sulphate and ascorbic acid with dichloramine-T. They give a very sharp colour change at the equivalence point. Arsenic(III) and iron(II) are suggested for the standardisation of dichloramine-T solutions.

DICHLORAMINE-T (DCT), *N,N'*-dichloro-*p*-toluene sulphonamide was proposed as an oxidant for the determination of a variety of compounds in non-aqueous and aqueous media¹⁻⁶. Only starch indicator which has several disadvantages⁷ has been used in titrations with DCT. For the first time we have proposed seven redox indicators in titrations with DCT. This paper describes the development of two new methods for the standardisation of DCT solutions and for the determination of arsenic(III), iron(II), antimony(III), hydroquinone, hydrazinium sulphate and ascorbic acid with DCT using naphthidine (N), 3,3'-dimethylnaphthidine (DMN), 3,3'-dimethylnaphthidinedisulphonic acid (DMNS), *O*-dianisidine (ODA), quinoline yellow (QY), diphenylbenzidine (DB) and amaranth (AM) as indicators.

Experimental

A 0.1% (w/v) solution of N and DMN in glacial acetic acid, DMNS⁸, QY and AM in water, DB in conc. sulphuric acid and ODA in 0.5% sulphuric acid was prepared and stored in amber bottles.

A standard solution of arsenic(III)⁹ and approximately 0.1*N* solutions of iron(II)¹⁰, antimony(III)¹¹, hydroquinone¹², hydrazinium sulphate⁸, ascorbic acid¹³ and DCT² were prepared and standardised by the recommended methods. A 10% (w/v) aqueous solution of potassium bromide was prepared. Working solutions were made by suitable dilution of the stock solutions.

General Procedures :

Standardisation of DCT solution against arsenic(III) and iron(II) : 20 ml of 0.1-0.02*N* arsenic(III) or iron(II) solution, 3 ml of 10% potassium bromide solution and *x* ml of 0.1% indicator solution [0.3 ml of QY or 0.05 ml of DB or AM for arsenic(III) and 0.1 ml of ODA for iron(II)] were diluted to 40 ml with distilled water for arsenic(III) or with phosphoric acid to give 2-5*M* at the end-point for iron(II) and titrated against 0.1-0.02*N* DCT solution to the appearance or disappearance of a colour. The results are given in Table 1.

Titration of 0.1-0.02*N* antimony(III), hydrazinium sulphate, hydroquinone and ascorbic acid : 10 ml of

TABLE 1—STANDARDISATION OF DCT SOLUTION

Strength of DCT solution found by*

Potentiometric Arsenic(III) method	Iodometric method	Arsenic(III) method	Iron(II) method
0.1209	0.1212	0.1208	0.1213
0.1184	0.1181	0.1183	0.1187
0.0992	0.0989	0.0991	0.0989
0.05926	0.05928	0.05925	0.05928
0.05581	0.05579	0.05580	0.05582
0.05265	0.05264	0.05265	0.05266
0.02632	0.02634	0.02632	0.02636
0.02226	0.02230	0.02225	0.02228

* Average of four determinations.

antimony(III) or hydrazinium sulphate or 20 ml of hydroquinone, 3 ml of 10% potassium bromide solution and *x* ml of 0.1% indicator [0.1 ml of AM for antimony(III) and hydrazinium sulphate and 0.2 ml of N or ODA for hydroquinone] were diluted with sulphuric acid to give a concentration of 1*M* at the end-point and titrated against 0.1-0.02*N* DCT solution to the appearance or disappearance of a colour.

20 ml of ascorbic acid, 3 ml of 10% potassium bromide solution and 0.1 ml of 0.1% DB, N, DMN, DMNS or AM or 0.2 ml of 0.1% QY or ODA were diluted with distilled water to 40 ml and titrated against 0.1-0.05*N* DCT solution. In titrations with 0.02*N* DCT solution, 2*M* phosphoric acid medium was used with indicator. The titration conditions, colour changes at the end-point and results are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The formal redox potential of the DCT-sulphonamide couple in glacial acetic acid medium is 1.2 V². N, DMN, DMNS, ODA and DB undergo a two-electron oxidation to a red or violet intermediate which is believed to be a diradical dication¹⁴. Formal redox potentials of N, DMN, DMNS and ODA were reported to be 922, 776, 838 and 849 mV, respectively.

Standardisation of DCT solutions : Iodometric method is the only titrimetric method proposed for the standardisation of DCT solutions. It uses starch

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF ARSENIC(III), IRON(II), ANTIMONY(III), HYDROQUINONE, HYDRAZINIUM SULPHATE AND ASCORBIC ACID WITH DICHLORAMINE-T

Sl. No.	Reductant taken mg	Medium	Indicator	DCT (N)	Reductant determined mg	Colour change at the end-point
1.	Arsenic(III) 75.23	H ₂ O + HAc + 0.5-1.7% KBr	DB	0.1	75.16	DB : Colourless to blue-violet AM : Red to colourless QY : Yellow to colourless
	37.84	"	AM	0.05	37.92	
	8.63	H ₂ O + HAc + 0.2-1.2% KBr	QY	0.02	8.64	
2.	Iron(II) 112.62	2-3M H ₃ PO ₄ + HAc + 0.5-2.5% KBr	ODA	0.1	112.98	Colourless to red
	55.81	" " "		0.05	55.81	
	7.42	" " "		0.02	7.45	
3.	Antimony(III) 61.13	1-3M H ₂ SO ₄ + HAc + 0.33-1.32% KBr	AM	0.10	61.17	Red to colourless
	30.87	" " "		0.05	30.86	
	2.38	" " "		0.02	2.36	
4.	Hydroquinone 109.74	0.5-2M H ₂ SO ₄ + HAc + 0.5-3.3% KBr	N	0.1	109.62	N : Light yellow to pinkish red ODA : Light yellow to orange-red
	56.21	0.5-1.5M H ₂ SO ₄ + HAc + 0.5-3.3% KBr		0.05	56.19	
	1.17	0.5-2M H ₂ SO ₄ + HAc + 0.17-1.7% KBr 0.5-1.5M H ₂ SO ₄ + HAc + 0.17-1.7% KBr	N ODA	0.02	1.18	
5.	Hydrazinium sulphate 31.54	1-2M H ₂ SO ₄ + HAc + 0.33-2.48% KBr	AM	0.1	31.57	Red to colourless
	18.74	" " " "		0.05	18.78	
	1.31	" " " "		0.02	1.32	
6.	Ascorbic acid 178.83	H ₂ O + HAc + 0.33-2.48% KBr	N DMN DMNS ODA DB QY AM	0.1	178.86	N, DMN, DMNS : Colourless to pink ODA : Colourless to orange-red DB : Colourless to blue-violet QY : Yellow to colourless AM : Red to colourless
	17.67	" " "		0.05	17.59	
	1.42	" " "		0.02	1.41	

indicator which has several disadvantages⁷. We have now developed two accurate methods for the standardisation of DCT solutions using the primary standard arsenic(III) oxide and standardised iron(II) solution.

Of the seven indicators examined, only QY, DB and AM function in the titration of arsenic(III) with DCT in aqueous medium. QY gives reversible end-point. The concentration of potassium bromide in the reaction mixture (60 ml) is 0.5-1.7% in the titration of 0.1-0.05N arsenic(III) and 0.2-1.2% in the titration of 0.02N arsenic(III). The reaction mixture is acidified to about 5M at the end-point as DCT in glacial acetic acid is added from the burette. QY changes colour from yellow to colourless, AM from red to colourless and DB from colourless to blue-violet at the end-point. The sharpness of the end-points is in the order DB > QY > AM.

A 0.3-0.5 ml of 0.1% QY, 0.05-0.2 ml of 0.1% DB or 0.05-0.25 ml of 0.1% AM is necessary in a total volume of 60 ml for proper indicator action in the titration of 0.1-0.05N arsenic(III) and 0.1-0.3 ml of 0.1% QY, 0.05-0.15 ml of 0.1% DB or 0.05-0.15 ml of 0.1% AM is necessary in the titration of 0.02N arsenic(III). Higher concentrations of the indicator

give overshoot end-points. The indicator correction has been found to be 0.03 ml of 0.01N DCT for 0.05 ml of 0.1% DB or AM. The proposed method has been used for the determination of arsenic(III) present in commercial samples of arsenic(III) oxide. The results given in Table 2 compare favourably with those obtained by the potentiometric method⁸ and cerium(IV) sulphate method^{1,5}.

Only ODA gives sharp and reversible colour change from colourless to red at the equivalence point in the titration of 0.1-0.02N iron(II) with DCT in 2-3M phosphoric acid medium containing potassium bromide. The concentration of potassium bromide is 0.5-2.5% in the titration of 0.1-0.05N iron(II) and 0.3-1.7% in the titration of 0.02N iron(II). At lower acidities and higher concentrations of potassium bromide sluggish end-points are obtained and at higher acidities premature end-points are obtained. A 0.05-0.2 ml of 0.1% ODA solution in a total volume of 60 ml gives a satisfactory colour change at the end-point. Higher concentrations of ODA give overshoot end-points. The red colour is stable for 45-90 min. The indicator correction has been found to be 0.02 ml of 0.01N DCT solution for 0.1 ml of 0.1% ODA. The method of standardisation of DCT with iron(II) has

been employed for the determination of iron in the commercial samples of iron(II) salts. The results presented in Table 2 compare favourably with those obtained by the dichromate method¹⁰.

Comparison of standard substances : The results in Table 1 show that satisfactory agreement exists among the three methods of standardisation. The titrations were carried out against the two primary standard substances arsenic(III) and potassium dichromate indirectly through the agency of a standardised ammonium iron(II) sulphate solution and a standardised sodium thiosulphate solution. It is of interest to note that arsenic(III) and iron(II) used in this investigation were titrated with a solution of cerium(IV) sulphate according to the established procedures and were found to give concordant results. The excellent consistency existing between the two standard substances indicates the validity of the proposed methods for standardisation of DCT solutions. Arsenic(III) method has some advantages over iodometric and iron(II) methods in that the primary standard arsenic(III) is directly titrated and its indicator and potentiometric titre values are concordant.

Titration of antimony(III) : Antimony(III) is quantitatively oxidised by DCT to antimony(V) in a two-electron change in sulphuric acid medium containing bromide. In the titration of a 0.1-0.02N antimony(III) solution only AM gives sharp irreversible colour change from red to colourless at the end-point in 1-3M sulphuric acid solution (60 ml) containing 0.33-1.32% potassium bromide and 0.1-0.5 ml of the indicator [0.1-0.4 ml for 0.02N Sb(III)]. Higher concentrations of sulphuric acid, indicator or potassium bromide give higher titre values. Lower concentrations of potassium bromide cause premature end-points.

The average indicator correction has been found to be 0.03 ml of 0.01N DCT solution for 0.1 ml of 0.1% AM. The results in Table 2 show that the values compare favourably with those obtained with bromate method¹¹.

Titration of hydroquinone : DCT oxidises hydroquinone to quinone instantaneously in sulphuric acid medium containing bromide at room temperature, the reaction involving a two-electron change. N and ODA give a reversible colour change from light yellow to pinkish red or orange red at the equivalence point. In the titration of 0.1-0.02N hydroquinone N gives sharp end-points in 0.5-2M sulphuric acid and ODA in 0.5-1.5M sulphuric acid. 60 ml of the titrated solution contains 0.5-3.3% potassium bromide in the titration of 0.1-0.05N hydroquinone and 0.17-1.7% potassium bromide in the titration of 0.02N hydroquinone. At lower acidities overshoot end-points are obtained. Higher acidities give sluggish end-points. Lower and higher concentrations of potassium bromide cause sluggish end-points. The stabilities of the end-point colours of N and ODA decrease with increasing acid concentration and are 3-5 and 5-20 min respectively.

In the titration of 0.1-0.05N hydroquinone,

0.1-0.4 ml of 0.1% ODA or 0.2-0.5 ml of 0.1% N is necessary for correct indicator action in a total volume of 60 ml. In the titration of 0.02N hydroquinone, 0.1-0.3 ml of 0.1% N or ODA is required. Higher concentrations of the indicator cause over titration. The average indicator correction has been found to be 0.03 ml of 0.01N DCT for 0.2 ml of 0.1% N and 0.1 ml of 0.1% ODA. N gives sharper end-points than ODA. The results presented in Table 2 compare favourably with those obtained with cerium(IV) sulphate method¹².

Titration of hydrazinium sulphate : Hydrazinium sulphate is quantitatively oxidised by DCT to nitrogen and water in four-electron change in sulphuric acid medium containing bromide at room temperature. Of the seven indicators only AM functions in the titration of 0.1-0.02N hydrazinium sulphate. Excellent end-points are obtained with 0.1-0.7 ml of 0.1% AM indicator in the titration of 0.1-0.05N hydrazinium sulphate in 1-2M sulphuric acid solution (60 ml) containing 0.33-2.48% potassium bromide. Very sharp end-points are obtained with 0.05-0.4 ml of 0.1% AM in the titration of 0.02N hydrazinium sulphate in 1-2M sulphuric acid solution (60 ml) containing 0.33-1.65% potassium bromide. The indicator gives premature end-points at lower acidities and overshoot end-points at higher acidities. The red colour of the indicator does not disappear at the end-point in lower concentrations of bromide and sharp end-points are not obtained at higher concentrations of bromide.

The indicator correction has been found to be 0.03 ml of 0.01N DCT for 0.05 ml of 0.1% AM.

The results in Table 2 compare favourably with those obtained by potentiometric method³.

Titration of ascorbic acid : DCT oxidises ascorbic acid quantitatively to dehydroascorbic acid in an aqueous medium at room temperature involving a two-electron oxidation. All the seven indicators N, DMN, DMNS, ODA, QY, DB and AM give very sharp end-points in the titration of 0.1-0.02N ascorbic acid in aqueous medium containing 0.33-2.48% potassium bromide. At the equivalence point N, DMN and DMNS change colour from colourless to pink, ODA from colourless to orange red, QY from yellow to colourless, DB from colourless to violet blue and AM from red to colourless. The end-point colours of N, DMN, DMNS, ODA and DB are stable for 3, 40, 15, 10 and 20 min respectively.

The amount of indicator required for the titration of 0.1-0.02N ascorbic acid solution (60 ml) is 0.05-0.25 ml of N, 0.05-0.3 ml of DMN, 0.05-0.2 ml of DMNS, 0.1-0.25 ml of ODA, 0.1-0.3 ml of QY and 0.05-0.15 ml of DB or AM. All the indicators except AM act as reversible indicators. Lower concentrations of bromide and higher concentrations of indicator give higher titre values. Premature end-points are obtained at higher concentrations of bromide.

The average indicator correction has been found to be 0.03 ml of 0.01N DCT solution for 0.05 ml of

0.1% AM and DB and 0.02 ml of 0.01N DCT solution for 0.05 ml of 0.1% N, DMN, DMNS, ODA and QY. The sharpness of the end-points is in the order DMNS > N > DMN = ODA = QY = DB > AM.

The results given in Table 2 show that they compare well with the iodate method¹⁸.

Applications of the ascorbic acid titration: The titration of ascorbic acid with DCT has been employed for the determination of ascorbic acid in vitamin C tablets and injections.

Assay of vitamin C tablets and injections: 20 tablets were weighed, powdered, dissolved in water and diluted to 100 ml in a standard flask such that each ml contains about 1 mg of ascorbic acid. In the case of injections, the requisite volume of the injection solution was diluted to 100 ml such that the ascorbic acid content is about 1 mg/ml. Aliquot of the tablet or injection solution was titrated with DCT under the conditions of titration of ascorbic acid. The results of the assay of tablets and injections presented in Table 3 compare favourably with

the quoted values and those obtained by the official method of British Pharmacopoeia¹⁶.

The synthetic mixtures containing ascorbic acid and tablet diluents and excipients were prepared and analysed. The results showed that 15 mg each of starch and citric acid and 10 mg each of sodium salt of alginic acid, stearic acid, glucose D, reserpine, gelatin, tartaric acid, oxalic acid, sucrose, stearic acid and gum acacia did not interfere in the determination of 10 mg of ascorbic acid.

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TABLE 3—ASSAY OF VITAMIN C TABLETS AND INJECTIONS

Tablet or Injection	Quoted mg	Amount of Ascorbic acid Found by	
		B.P method mg	Proposed method* mg
Citravite (Pharmed)	500	498.6	502.4
Sukcee (IDPL)	500	494.8	502.2
Ascorbicin (Sarabhai)	500	508.5	505.7
Sorvicin (East India)	500	495.6	502.3
Celin (Glaxo)	500	493.9	490.5
Redoxon (Roche)	500	487.2	492.4
Reclor (Sarabhai)	250	246.1	250.2
Calcium Sandoz 10% + Vit C (Sandoz India)	500	500.5	498.6
Redoxon (Roche)	500	498.5	500.4

* Average of six determinations.